

The Impact of Map Generalization with Multiple Spatial Data Levels on GIS Analyses

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

When representing spatial data and their attributes on different types of maps, the scale which is the numerical relationship between the ground extent and the mapped extent, plays a key role. In order to create a clear and legible map at different scale levels, map generalization techniques are used. Though current commercial mapping software packages are integrated with sophisticated tools and operations to prepare maps and to manage spatial data, users violate some basic theorems and concepts in cartography. They retrieve a data set and do the analysis part without considering very important characteristics such as the scale of the source data set, the purpose of what the original map is prepared and the degree of generalization of the data sets. Further, the GIS users use and combine different scaled data sets with different degrees of generalization. In this study, it attempts to find the impacts of map generalization on GIS analyses. Current study used two types of features with different spatial data levels for a simple GIS analysis. These digital data sets were prepared by the Survey Department of Sri Lanka with the scales of 1:10000, 1:50000 and 1: 250000. 09 combinations of data sets were used for the analysis through a model prepared using the model builder tool in the GIS package. This simple overlay operation was done to find the best location for a wild life park using three basic requirements. The study clearly shows that different results can be obtained for different combinations. It can be noticed different potential zones with the variations of the number, extent, X and Y coordinates of the Centroid and their perimeters. Therefore, study thoroughly recommends to GIS users to use different data layers with same scale and same degree of generalization in the analyses.

Keywords: MAP GENERALIZATION, SCALE, LEVEL OF DATA, GIS ANALYSIS

Introduction

For a long period of time, geospatial information and phenomena about the significant features on the earth's surface have been performed an important part of the human activities in organized societies (Kraak & Fabrikant 2017). They were, firstly, represented on paper maps with different scale levels for specific purposes such as management and development of natural resources, infrastructure development, rural

development and tourism (Roth et al 2017). Maps do not simply locate things. It is a sophisticated synthesis of physical geography and it leads user to think in a new way. The final output of a map is representing a meaningful picture of the reality (Dutton 1998). Therefore, it serves specially the aim of being a help in orientation in the terrain and by its supplementary annotations of conveying multi-faceted information (Jongepier et al 2016). Hence the process of map making is powerful, as it reveals insights, discoveries and new ways of understanding (Kraak & Fabrikant, 2017).

Traditionally, maps were generated manually by cartographers and it was a hard and fastidious work to maintain a good graphic quality, high image resolution and good placement of their symbols and labels (Kraak & Fabrikant, 2017). In the last two decades, innovative technologies have been greatly applied for experimental and operational activities in mapping and its related sciences (Zhan & Buttenfield, 1995 and Robinson et al, 2017). Nowadays, more and more maps are appeared on paper supports as well on the display screens of computers whose sizes are often reduced than its real size of the represented area (Weibel, 1995). Technological changes have been made the mapping and analysis of geographic information a daily part of how we understand the world. As a result of introducing computers into mapping technology, maps in digital forms became a very important form of input to a Geographical Information Systems (GIS) which is an excellent way to inventory geographic facts (Weibel & Buttenfield, 1988 and Lu et al. 2019). Since GISs have strong analytical capabilities, these digital maps are extremely essential as a common means to portray the results of an analysis (Wastfelt, 2020).

Almost always, maps take a less physical space than the real area that it represents. Due to the lack of space, the real world, as it is, cannot be expressed faithfully on the map sheet Wastfelt (2020). Therefore, maps are often scaled down to fit the display sizes. This reduction of size is reflected by the scale of the map and it is represented as a ratio or a graphic scale (Weibel & Dutton, 1999). This ratio indicates the relationship between the number of metric units on the ground and which is represented by a unit in the space of the map model to the map user (Harrie et al. 2002). Scale is considered as the most crucial mathematical feature of any map. The smaller the map scale the more the representation is simplified and abstracted (Weibel & Jones, 1998 and Zucker et al., 2000). Based on a desired scale, cartographers select real world objects or concepts and determine an appropriate way to depict them in map form (Weibel, 1995). The resulting map is effectively a visualization of spatially grounded information (Zhan & Buttenfield., 1995).

In every map, the features on the earth's surface are represented reduced. Since the map contents do not decrease proportionally in direct ratio to the reduction of the paper surface, an increasing density of the map contents arises at smaller scales (Wastfelt, 2020). The features on the map are approximately true to the reality only at larger scales and the representation is comparatively remote from the reality at smaller scales (Robinson et al, 2017). Furthermore, due to the limits of acuity of the human eye and the printing limits, this reduction of objects and forms in a map cannot be continued indefinitely. It should be terminated at where the

limit is reached. This is approximately, 0.02mm at a distance of 30cm from the eye (Imhof, 1982). Also it is not realistic to continue decreasing the size of map elements down to the just perceptible and printable limits (Maes, 1994).

Important objects which are having a close relationship with the map purpose should be immediately obvious, not just perceptible on a good representation (Weibel, 1995 and Rosenberg & Grafton, 2010). As well, the differences in form should be clearly distinguishable. Therefore, as geographic features fight for representation in the reduced map space, some features or their attributes in the original data set will need to be eliminated from the map or geometric changing operations need to be applied for the features or attributes those remaining further on the map to produce a good visualization (Lamy et al., 1999 and Wang et al, 2002). This process of creating a clear and legible map is known as map generalization (Buttenfield & McMaster, 1991). As a basic task in Cartography, map generalization allows the comprehensible visualization of geographic data at a reduced scale (Muller et al., 1995 and Regnaud, 2001).

In the process of map generalization, it includes some typical operations such as reduction in the details of lines, areas and volumes; deletion of less important features, exaggeration of the size of features that would otherwise too small, amalgamation of adjacent features, collapse in the dimensionality of area features to lines or points, caricature of the shape and pattern of simplified map features to communicate their original form, and displacement in order to retain adequate separation distances between adjacent features (Douglas & Peucker, 1973; Cromley, 1992; Wei et al, 2018 and Feng, et al., 2019).

During the process of generalization, cartographer should keep several factors in mind in order to achieve proper results. Apart from the scale of the map, the most important is the purpose of the map and its audience (Kraak & Ormeling, 2003). The factors such as the geographical region that needs to be mapped and the taste and knowledge of the cartographer would be considered as well, when generalizing from one spatial data set to another data set (Doihara et al., 2002). The scale of the source material which has to be generalized, special conditions for legibility, symbol specification, choice of colors and technical reproduction capabilities such as printing processes would be key factors in deciding the degree of generalization. Maintaining the geometric and attribute accuracy, as well as the aesthetic quality of the map is also very important in the process of map generalization (Kraak & Ormeling, 2003). However, the final goal of map generalization is to stress the salient objects while omitting the less important features or attributes with respect to the scale and the purpose of the map (Galanda, 2003).

Map generalization usually involves a great deal of analysis of the geographic data for deciding what and how to represent them in the map with an effective manner (Nickerson, 1988). Since the generalization is a subjective activity, it is difficult to set up fixed rules although experiments attempting to do so manifold (Kraak & Ormeling, 2003). The most of generalization processes are carried out manually by trained

cartographers. This process is a labor intensive process and depends mainly on cartographer's experience, possible knowledge of the area, natural intuition, taste and skills (Gashi et al., 2018).

To satisfy the map requirements such as geometrical, topological, contextual, cultural and procedural, McMaster (1989) defined a comprehensive number of cartographic operations. Thereby they describe the operations extensively and further differentiate between point, line and area operations. After this attempt, Galanda (2003); Ware et.al. (2003); Gulgen & Gokgoz (2008); Raheja et al. (2010); Touya (2018); Muller & Wang (1992); Openshaw & Openshaw (1997) and Topfer & Pillewizer, (1966) extended the list of operations mainly focusing on the generalization of area features.

Reclassification – This operation changes the class of an object. Usually one classifies to a more abstract class. For an example, an area of deciduous forest would be reclassified into a forest after this operation (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The function of Reclassification operator

Aggregation – This combines disjoint map objects to one new object by bridging the space between them (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The function of Aggregation operator

Amalgamation / Merge – These two operations which have the same meanings in generalization would combine adjacent objects to new one object (Figure 3).

Figure 3: The function of Amalgamation/ Merge operator

Typification – It reduces the complexity of the group of objects by eliminating, displacing, enlarging and aggregating the individual objects, whereby the typical object arrangement is maintained (Figure 4).

Figure 4: The function of Typification operator

Displacement – Denotes the movement of an entire object. It is specially designed to maintain the clarity of the map and it remains the original shape of the object (Figure 5).

Figure 5: The function of Displacement operator

Collapse – This operation collapses a polygon either to a line or to a point or a double line feature into a single line feature (Figure 6).

Figure 6: The function of Collapse operator

Elimination – The elimination operator removes one or more objects from the data set. The freed space may

be assigned to neighboring objects or left empty (Figure 7).

Figure 7: The function of Elimination operator

Enlargement – This operator deals with the global increase of an object (Figure 8).

Figure 8: The function of Enlargement operator

Exaggeration – It defines a local displacement of object parts and it leads to a shape distortion. It can be induced by distance conflicts with other objects or by internal distance conflicts (Figure 9).

Figure 9: The function of Exaggeration operator

Symbolization – The visual representation of the foot print of an object would be replaced by a pictorial symbol. These symbols are having special characteristics and the colour and the shape of the symbol is very similar to the replaced object (Figure 10).

Figure 10: The function of Symbolization operator

Simplification – The simplification operator reduces the granularity of an outline by removing insignificant crenulations (Figure 11).

Figure 11: The function of Simplification operator

Smoothing – This improves the visual appearance of an object’s outline (Figure 12).

Figure 12: The function of Symbolization operator

The consequences of generalization are complex. It means that the generalization of one feature affects on other features and ultimately alters the quality of the end results derived from a GIS. The errors produced by generalization are very difficult to quantify, because the amount of error can depend on the type of feature and also the complexity of the feature (Thapa & Bossler, 1992). Generalization potentially causes unintended transformations of the data that alter the topology of geographical phenomena and effect subsequent statistical or geometrical calculations(McMaster, 1987). As a result of different degrees of generalization used in different scaled maps, qualitatively the feature’s characteristics, and quantitatively feature’s position, number of features, line lengths and line sinuosity, sizes of areas covered by polygon features and their shapes can be changed(Muller, 1990; Muller, 1991 and Jiang & Claramunt, 2004). Normally, GIS users would want to minimize, control and quantify the effects of generalization on their results(Grunreich, 1993 and Kulyk

&Sossa, 2018). Hence knowledge about the type and magnitude of generalization effects within spatial data sets is essential by any GIS user.

Presently, in the activities related to geo information, use of GIS has been dramatically increased. And it has been converted into a common and popular discipline even among the general public (Grunreich, 1993). They use GIS software packages and their tools and models to solve their daily activities such as finding a place, finding the best route and finding the closest service. In these scenarios, the most of the general GIS users utilized GIS packages and concepts for their problem solving activities without having a prior knowledge about the theories and its inherent concepts (Grunreich, 1993).

Principally, it is well agreed that GIS users should not violate some principles in geo information sciences. Further, they have to obey those rules and regulations in the theoretical aspects in not only GIS but also other mapping related sciences such as cartography and surveying sciences as well. Unfortunately, what the current GIS users do is that they collect some maps which may be products from different mapping agencies, with different scale levels, which may be the products of either digital format or paper format and which were prepared to different purposes (Kraak & Ormeling, 2003 and Robinson, 1982). And after that, they prepare models and use different tools in GIS packages for the analysis part.

Although the data contained in a GIS do not have a specific scale, since the user can easily change the scale by zooming in and out, all spatial data have a specific resolution associated with their original collection. The resolution is that of the digitized map, when the data were obtained by digitizing. And also, it is the pixel size, if the data were obtained from imagery. Current GIS spatial databases are often created from digitizing existing analogue maps which, in turn, have been made by manual cartographic generalization methods. As a consequence of this, most digital databases have generalization effects embedded within them that have been derived from manual generalization. The different types of generalization effects that features have suffered are compounded when features are used in a GIS analysis. These effects can have important consequences on the results of typical GIS map manipulations.

If GIS users use maps with different scales, those maps may be coming with different generalization levels. For an example, the following case study can be considered. It is assumed that a GIS user wants to find the best location to establish a bank in an area given. After considering the factors such as access, land use, distance to other banks, population density and locations of government and private working places, by using a simple analysis in GIS, this problem can be solved easily. However, the datasets can be prepared with different scale levels as shown in the Table 1 by various authorities.

Detail	Scale
Access	1:10,000
Land use	1:25,000
Locations of other banks	1:10,000
Population data	1:50,000
Buildings	1:5,000

Table 1: Different Scales for Features

In this scenario, these maps have been prepared with different levels of data. It means that road dataset, other banks data and buildings data are very closed to the real surface, but land use data is much away from the reality and population data file is far away from the reality, according to their scales. In the process of generalization, when the cartographer prepares the population map, since he has not enough space, he would omit a lot of data. It means that these effects would influence to the final analysis badly. Therefore, there should be a reasonable method to overcome these problems in this scenario. It means that user has to aware about the effects and the consequences of cartographic generalization and its operators. In this study, it is going to discuss about the generalization effects and their impacts in GIS analysis as the primary objective.

Materials and methods

Three types of digital data sets: 1:10000 (10K), 1:50000 (50K) and 1:250000 (250K) National Topographic maps, prepared by Survey Department of Sri Lanka, were used which are having mainly three different levels of details (scales). Survey Department of Sri Lanka acts as the National Mapping Agency of Sri Lanka and has the sole authority to prepare and modify series of maps using ground surveying (Plane table surveying technique) and air borne surveying (Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing) techniques. Further it produces 1:5000 and 1:2000 scale level maps for selected urban areas.

Data to produce the maps of 1:2000, 1:5000 and 1:10000 have been collected using photogrammetric technique, 1:50000 maps have been prepared by manual generalizing and manual digitizing the one inch sheets (scale of 1:63360) which were produced by plane table surveying technique. And the data for 1:250000 maps have been collected from one inch sheets through manual methods. It means that data for different scaled maps have been taken from different methods. These maps have been updated separately and the process leads data redundancy and inconsistencies. And also it increases the data collection costs and the time, since three map series are undergoing to update separately.

The 1:10000 digital dataset has been created by digitizing the 1:10000 National Topographic Maps. It consisted with eleven thematic layers: building features, transportation network, administration boundaries, hydrographic network, reserves, land use features, terrain relief, utility network, place names, geodetic control

network and grids. In the data set, buildings have been represented as polygon features, transportation network is represented by line features with the center lines of them. 1:50000 maps have been created by digitizing the national map series of 1:50000. It is also consisted with all layers as in the 1:10000 dataset but except the utility network. Since the geographic features are fighting for the space on the map sheet, the building features are represented as point features in this map series.

Since data plays a vital role in GIS discipline, the users mostly, do not consider the levels of data sets. What they do is collect the data sets from a data source, and do the analysis. Normally, GIS users and analysts do not worry about the level of the data set. They, sometimes, combine two or more different levels of data together which leads to violate some general principles of cartography. According to the principles of cartography, data features with different levels cannot be combined together and if we want to combine them together, we have to prepare the dataset.

In this study, it was used two types of features such as roads and rivers for the analysis which are represented using different scales such as 1:10000, 1:50000 and 1:250000. River data set for the study area was consisted with two features as shown in the Figure 13 at the scale of 1:10000, Figure 14 at 1:50000 and Figure 15 at 1:250000. Further, the road feature was consisted with a network with two road segments (Figure 16 at the scale of 1:10000, Figure 17 at 1:50000 and Figure 18 at 1:250000) It means that the analyst the freedom to use different combinations.

Figure 13: River layer at 10k scale

Figure 14: River layer at 50k scale

Figure 15: River layer at 250k scale

Figure 16: Road layer at 10k scale

Figure 19: GIS Model for the Preliminary Study

Table 2: Different Combinations of Scales of Data.

Combination Number	Different combinations	
	River	Road
01	1:10000	1:10 000
02	1:10000	1:50000
03	1:10000	1:250000
04	1:50000	1:10000
05	1:50000	1:50000
06	1:50000	1:250000
07	1:250000	1:10000
08	1:250000	1:50000
09	1:250000	1:250000

Results and analysis

Overlay operation was repeated for different combinations. The results of overlay operations from the different combinations of scales were compared with the results of which the same scale maps which were used for the study. Furthermore, they were compared with the results of the combination of 1: 10000 scaled map for all three layers, since it is the scale which is used as the scale of the source material in the multiple representative databases. In the analysis part of the results of different combinations, the Number of resulted

Potential Zones for a wild life park, their Areas, X and Y Coordinates of the Centroid and the Perimeters were compared.

10K Road Data Vs River Data Combinations

Overlay operation was done firstly with 10K road data and 10k, 50k and 250k river data combinations. GIS based model which was designed for overlay analysis was run for different levels of data sets and the results were analyzed. The results from both 10k data layers were very important, as it is the scale which is going to maintain in the Multiple Representative Data Bases (MRDBs).

Figure 20: Results of 10k Road Data Vs 10k River Data

Figure 21: Results of 10k Road Data Vs 50k River Data

Figure 22: Results of 10k Road Data Vs 250k River Data

The graphical view of the results illustrates that even though the number of potential zones for a wild life park is same for all combinations of 10k road data with different scaled river data, it can be seen significant changes in their extents, shapes and locations (Table 3.2).

Table 3: Results from different combinations of 10k data with 10k, 50k and 250k

Combination	Potential Zones	Area (m ²)	X Coordinate (m)	Y Coordinate (m)	Perimeter (m)
10k Road Vs 10k River	Zone 01	315 123	195 202	159 612	3 246
	Zone 02	316 012	199 460	156 417	3 001
	Zone 03	1 585 756	193 693	157 900	10 405
10k Road Vs 50k River	Zone 01	241 599	195 163	159 598	3 265
	Zone 02	367 741	199 423	156 411	3 024
	Zone 03	1 637 808	193 764	157 781	10 070
10k Road Vs 250k River	Zone 01	105 197	194 938	159 646	2 364
	Zone 02	942 019	198 401	156 887	9 411
	Zone 03	1 680 493	193 817	157 830	10 215

50K Road Data Vs River Data Combinations

The results from the combinations of 50k road data with different scaled river data declared that when the analyst uses different combinations of scales, a mixture of results would be obtained. Table 3.3 shows their variations in number of zones, their extents, shapes and locations. When it gives 5 potential zones by the 50k road and 10k river combination, other two combinations give only 4 zones.

Figure 23: Results of 50k Road Data Vs 10k River Data

Figure 24: Results of 50k Road Data Vs 50k River Data

Figure 25: Results of 50k Road Data Vs 250k River Data

Table 4: Results from different combinations of 50k data with 10k, 50k and 250k

Combination	Potential Zones	Area (m ²)	X Coordinate (m)	Y Coordinate (m)	Perimeter (m)
50k Road Vs 10k River	Zone 01	2 140 172	194 628	158 141	18 669
	Zone 02	474 847	195 198	159 558	3 675
	Zone 03	225 318	199 446	156 371	2 546
	Zone 04	307 061	195 088	156 569	2 543
	Zone 05	1 058 305	193 102	158 388	6 856
50k Road Vs 50k River	Zone 01	2 199 177	194 739	157 984	18 058
	Zone 02	424 911	195 169	159 535	3 724
	Zone 03	274 617	199 403	156 369	2 624
	Zone 04	1 451 672	193 664	157 821	10 177

50k Road	Zone 01	2 460 431	195 275	157 704	22 412
Vs	Zone 02	247 838	194 973	159 574	3 058
250k River	Zone 03	727 084	198 476	156 815	8 940
	Zone 04	1 485 510	193 757	157 827	10 413

250K Road Data Vs River Data Combinations

Again it proved the effects of map generalization in GIS manipulations severely, in the combinations of 250k road data and different levels of river data. It gives very terrible results in this stage, specially in the case of 250k road and 250k river combination, as it is the greatest degree of generalization which is applied for the data.

Figure 26: Results of 250k Road Data Vs 10k River Data

Figure 27: Results of 250k Road Data Vs 50k River Data

Figure 28: Results of 250k Road Data Vs 250k River Data

The results of the analysis show the clear deviations from the different scale combinations. It can be assumed that if the analyst has selected the same scale for the different data shape files, it can be selected that combination as the best possible way to do an analysis. In this study, 10k data combination can be taken as the best option, since it is the largest scale from three scales. When other results were compared with this combination, it can be seen that a lot of changes are there. These changes can be seen in the number of output clusters, their shapes, their orientation, the location of the clusters.

In the case of the combination of 10k road data with different river data, it was only three resulted clusters in all combinations. But it can be seen several changes in their sizes, and locations. The results which are from the combination of 50k Road data and different River data, show different number of clusters. And it was resulted different shapes with different sizes at different locations. When the combinations with 250k road data were overlayed with different scaled river data, different number of clusters with different geometric characteristics were resulted.

Table 5: Results from different combinations of 250k data with 10k, 50k and 250k

Combination	Potential Zones	Area (m ²)	X Coordinate (m)	Y Coordinate (m)	Perimeter (m)
250k Road Vs 10k River	Zone 01	2 126 401	194 413	158 390	16 893
	Zone 02	738 573	195 471	159 331	4 900
	Zone 03	253 190	195 125	156 319	3 553
	Zone 04	1 048 710	193 091	158 396	6 325
250k Road Vs 50k River	Zone 01	2 134 862	194 541	158 272	16 499
	Zone 02	717 777	195 470	159 293	4 993
	Zone 03	132 920	199 311	156 335	2 183

	Zone 04	269 872	195 102	156 335	2 936
	Zone 05	1 014 440	193 110	158 319	6 386
250k Road Vs 250k River	Zone 01	429 331	195 286	159 314	4 036
	Zone 02	184 318	198 481	156 812	2 782
	Zone 03	160 263	199 444	156 209	1 863
	Zone 04	1 290 932	193 626	157 924	10 875

It means that different results with different geometries can be obtained, from various combinations of scaled data. This is the problem what was discussed in this study. The study clearly identified that this issue is a considerable factor in any kind of GIS analysis. The analyst, normally, do not consider this issue knowingly or unknowingly. It is a must to take this issue into considerations.

Conclusion

The study identified that there are some considerable changes in the results obtained from the different combinations of two data sets. It was able to recognize a number of reasons for these differences. The study identified the impact of feature displacement, elimination, exaggeration, enhancement and change of geometry as the result of map generalization processes, is the main responsible factor for those differences in GIS map manipulations.

With the rapid development in GIS sector, it is increasing the number of users day by day with or without having the cartography knowledge. The main problem is that the users do not have any basic knowledge about the map making processes and sometimes, they do not aware about the effects. What they do is they just convert paper maps into a digital copy by digitizing it and do the analysis part. Sometimes, knowingly or unknowingly, they use digital maps which can be easily found, without considering the scale of the source material. For an example, they use 250k data layers for an analysis which should maintain a higher accuracy level. Further, combining different levels of data sets, for an example use of 10k road data with 50k river data, is very common among GIS analysts. Therefore, these applications finally fail and create various types of problems.

The study suggests that there must be having a systematic approach to overcome the effects of generalization in GIS manipulations. This approach may be having different precautions to control the effects. It would be having processes in the data preparation stage (the process of data enrichment) as well as in the operation stage (the process of selecting different generalization tools, their parameters, order of them and selecting the best suitable tolerance values). In order to achieve successful results from any operation or any analysis using GIS processes, it is clear that the generalization procedure should be applied as a pre- processing stage. With

the intention to overcome the matters arising when using the same type of data sets with different degrees of generalization or working with different data sets that are represented by two scales, which were discussed in the previous chapter, a model of generalization using existing tools in ArcGIS software was developed in this study.

The study suggested that it has to develop some models in GIS environment to address this issue. This kind of model should have the property to totally handle and control by the user or the GIS analyst, who, sometimes, may not be aware about the cartographic generalization theories and its relative aspects. The steps have being designed to take decisions by the analyst at various stages of pre processing data with number of options. The advantage of the model is, since it gives several options in various stages, that the user can decide whether the results of any tool are going to be applied to the existing data set or ignore the results when the user is not satisfied about the results from any tool in the model. Further, it is suggesting that rules and regulations should be prepared and implemented to overcome these issues. It has to give the authority to the Survey Department of Sri Lanka to prepare and revise the maps as the National Mapping Agency. It has to have some models to create different scaled maps according to the user requirements. And also, it is suggesting that proper revisions for the maps should be implemented.

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